

Possible Antiparkinsonian Compounds. Part VI Synthesis of Aryl-N-phthaloyl-glycinates/dl- α alaninates and their Ketones

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N-Phthaloyl-glycine and N-phthaloyl-dl- α -alanine have been condensed with phenol, p-cresol and β -naphthol to yield aryl-N-phthaloyl-glycinates/dl- α -alaninates with a view to test their anti-parkinsonian activity. The esters were further converted into the corresponding ketones by Fries-rearrangement.

THE antiparkinsonian activity of glycine itself has been reported by Woert and Hadzovic¹. These authors reported that 200-400 mg/kg. glycine relieved the hind limbs rigidity in rats. Further aminoalkyl-carboxylate esters have been found very effective in antagonising the symptoms of Parkinson's disease². In view of these observations, the authors undertook the study of aryl-N-phthaloyl-glycinates/dl- α -alaninates and their corresponding ketones obtained by Fries-rearrangement.

Experimental

N-Phthaloyl amino-acids

N-Phthaloyl-glycine and N-phthaloyl-dl- α -alanine required in the present synthesis were obtained following the method of Vogel³.

Aryl-N-phthaloyl-glycinates/dl- α -alaninates

A mixture of N-phthaloyl-amino-acid viz., N-phthaloyl-glycine and N-phthaloyl-dl- α -alanine, (0.01 mole) and phenol viz., phenol, β -naphthol and p-cresol (0.01 mole) was heated in a bath till a clear solution was obtained. Phosphorous-oxychloride (0.016 mole) was then added slowly with constant shaking. After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr under anhydrous conditions. Towards the end of the reaction HCl gas ceased to evolve. The contents were cooled and washed with sodium-bicarbonate solution to remove unreacted acid into the acid chloride. The brown gummy mass was obtained which was triturated with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and then recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	H	phenyl	76-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ NO ₄	4.98	4.52
2.	H	p-cresyl	61-2	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.74	4.28
3.	H	β -naphthyl	100-1	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.22	4.21
4.	CH ₃	phenyl	89-90	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.74	4.30
5.	CH ₃	p-cresyl	81-82	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₄	4.53	4.32
6.	CH ₃	β -naphthyl	109-	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ NO ₄	4.05	4.18

Note: Melting points are uncorrected. Solvent used for the recrystallisation was ethanol. The per cent yield ranged from 50-55%.

Conversion of the esters into the ketones by Fries-rearrangement

Aryl-N-phthaloyl-glycinate/dl- α -alaninate (0.003 mole) and anhydrous aluminium-chloride (0.005 mole) were heated at 135°-140° for six hours under anhydrous conditions. The reaction mixture was poured

TABLE—2

Sl. No.	Rearranged Product	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis		Phenyl hydrazone Analysis		
				% Nitrogen		M.P. °C	% Nitrogen	
				Calcd.	Found		Calcd.	Found
1.	Phthalimido-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl-ketone	98-9	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ NO ₄	4.98	4.55	185-6	11.32	11.18
2.	Phthalimido-methyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl-ketone	81-2	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.74	4.52	170-1	10.90	10.88
3.	α -(phthalimido-methyl)- β -hydroxy-naphthyl-ketone	149	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.22	4.01	160-1	9.97	9.64
4.	α -(phthalimido-ethyl)-2-hydroxy-phenyl-ketone	104-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₄	4.74	4.44	188-9	10.90	10.58
5.	α -(phthalimido-ethyl)-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl-ketone	102-3	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₄	4.53	4.11	155-6	10.52	10.69
6.	α -(phthalimido-ethyl)- β -hydroxy-naphthyl-ketone	175	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ NO ₄	4.05	8.92	198-9	9.65	9.28

Note : The above compounds were recrystallised from dilute ethanol. Per cent yield ranged from 30-40.

into the crushed ice containing 100 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. A yellow solid separated out which was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from dilute ethanol.

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